

THERAPEUTIC DIET: THE ROLE OF WHOLE-FOODS AND PLANT-BASED DIET IN AUTOIMMUNE DISEASES MODULATION

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Abstract

Autoimmune diseases represent a diverse group of chronic conditions marked by immune system dysfunction, with rising prevalence globally. Emerging evidence suggests that diet plays a pivotal role not only in symptom modulation but also in potentially altering disease progression. This review explores the clinical and mechanistic implications of whole-foods and plant-based diets as a therapeutic strategy for managing autoimmune conditions. Drawing on data from observational studies, randomized controlled trials, and individual case reports, it examines the impact of dietary interventions on diseases such as rheumatoid arthritis, type 1 diabetes, multiple sclerosis, inflammatory bowel disease, systemic lupus erythematosus, and psoriatic arthritis. Findings consistently point to reductions in inflammatory markers, improved gut microbiota profiles, and attenuation of disease symptoms. While complete reversal of autoimmune pathology remains uncertain, the data support whole-foods and plant-based diets as a sustainable, adjunct approach capable of enhancing clinical outcomes. The review also addresses implementation challenges and emphasizes the need for further large-scale research to validate these preliminary findings and optimize dietary recommendations within personalized treatment frameworks.

Introduction

Autoimmune disorders are the conditions in which the body mistakenly attack its own body cells. In autoimmune disorder our body cannot differentiate between harmful pathogens and healthy cells. These are the family of at least 80 diseases resulting from various factors such as environmental (lifestyle, diet, drugs, infections) and some of genetic factors [1]. The incidence of Autoimmune disorders approximately 3–5% worldwide, is increasing in westernized societies, as confirmed by epidemiological studies; these suggest that multiple sclerosis, type 1 diabetes, inflammatory bowel diseases (mainly Crohn's disease), systemic lupus erythematosus, primary biliary cirrhosis, myasthenia gravis, autoimmune thyroiditis, hepatitis, and rheumatic diseases are steadily increasing [2]. Rheumatoid arthritis is diagnosed between the ages of

30 and 60 years, while psoriasis is diagnosed between 15 and 35 years of age. These are a small minority of the vast number of autoimmune diseases that affect 20% of the entirety of the human population. There are over 100 types of autoimmune diseases that predominantly affect women. Approximately 80% of all patients diagnosed with autoimmune diseases are women [3]. Several studies have identified the role of diet in initiation and progression of as well as in protection against autoimmunity [4]. It has been found that some fatty acids such as eicosanoids and polyunsaturated fatty acids, especially omega-3, can affect the immunoregulatory mechanisms [5]. Among premenopausal women diagnosed with lupus, variations in disease activity have been linked to differences in body mass index [6], Due to the side

effects commonly associated with standard drug therapies and their limited ability to target underlying causes, there is an increasing focus on lifestyle-focused approaches especially those centered around nutrition as alternative treatment options. An increasing number of studies suggest that adopting healthier lifestyle habits, particularly following plant-based diets can help reduce the risk of autoimmune diseases and alleviate existing symptoms associated with autoimmune conditions [7].

The science behind autoimmune disorders and diet

Among various environmental influences, diet plays a key role in shaping the composition of the gut microbiota. Growing evidence highlights the potential of using dietary strategies to modify gut microbiota as a promising approach for preventing and managing numerous health conditions, including rheumatoid arthritis [8]. In individuals with rheumatoid arthritis, consuming a diet rich in fiber have been shown to boost the production of anti-inflammatory short-chain fatty acids, reduce levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines, and positively influence the balance of gut microbiota [9].

What is a Whole-Food, Plant-Based Diet (WFPBD)?

A Whole-Food, Plant-Based Diet focuses on eating primarily unprocessed, plant-based foods and significantly reducing or eliminating animal products, added sugars, refined grains, and processed oils. The core of this dietary pattern includes:

A wide variety of vegetables and fruits

- Whole grains such as oats, brown rice, and quinoa
- Legumes like beans, lentils, and peas
- Nuts and seeds
- Plant-based sources of omega-3 fatty acids, including flaxseeds, chia seeds, walnuts, and algae

In comparison to omnivorous diets, vegetarian and plant-based diets that are high in whole grains, legumes, vegetables, fruits, nuts, and seeds have been linked to significant reductions in several modifiable risk factors. These include body mass index (BMI), waist circumference, atherogenic lipoprotein levels, blood glucose, inflammation, and blood pressure [10]. Plant-based diets are considered safe and beneficial across all life stages, including pregnancy, breastfeeding, childhood, and older adulthood. Rich in fiber and polyphenols, these diets are linked to a more diverse gut microbiome, which produces metabolites with anti-inflammatory properties that

may support the management of various health conditions [11].

A 2020 review by Islam et al. highlights those diets low in calories and protein, yet rich in fiber, polyunsaturated fats, vitamins, minerals, and polyphenols, may offer a nutritional profile beneficial for individuals with Systemic Lupus Erythematosus (SLE) [12]. In autoimmune diseases, polyunsaturated fatty acids are commonly found in foods like fish and oilseeds have shown potential in reducing inflammation. This effect occurs through their conversion into anti-inflammatory prostaglandins (such as E1 and E2), which play a role in modulating cytokine activity and guiding leukocyte movement. Notably, omega-3 fatty acids, including eicosapentanoic acid and docosahexaenoic acid, are key PUFAs that contribute to the regulation of the body's inflammatory processes [13]. Oxidative stress plays a significant role in the development and progression of various autoimmune diseases, including systemic lupus erythematosus, rheumatoid arthritis, vasculitis, systemic sclerosis, inflammatory myopathies, type 1 diabetes, multiple sclerosis, and Hashimoto's thyroiditis. Antioxidants, which are small and stable molecules, help combat this stress by donating electrons to neutralize harmful free radicals [14].

Mechanism of WFPD in autoimmune Disease reversal

In individuals with rheumatoid arthritis, disease activity appears to be influenced by dietary patterns. Vegan and lacto-vegetarian diets have been associated with beneficial changes in fatty acid profiles and improvements in symptoms, particularly when the diet is strictly followed, such as vegan plans rich in lactobacilli and raw, unprocessed foods. Both vegan and raw food diets have shown promising effects in reducing symptoms not only in rheumatoid arthritis but also in fibromyalgia patients [15].

Consumption of plant-based nutrients is associated with a reduction in systemic inflammation, while consumption of red meat and excessive dairy has the opposite effect and may increase risk of acute flares in those that suffer from certain chronic diseases like inflammatory bowel disease or psoriasis and certain cancers [16].

Research has shown that dietary strategies can influence inflammatory responses. Approaches such as calorie-restricted diets or increased intake of fruits and

vegetables have been effective in lowering the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines like IL-6 and TNF- α , as well as reducing markers such as C-reactive protein. Additionally, earlier studies have found that consuming high-fat meals can lead to a drop in leptin levels and an increase in inflammation-related markers, particularly IL-6, during the post-meal period [17].

Clinical Evidence: Whole-Food, plant-based Diets in specific Autoimmune Diseases

Rheumatoid Arthritis

Rheumatoid arthritis is a long-term autoimmune condition characterized by chronic inflammation, impacting about 1% of the global population. It typically affects joints on both sides of the body, most often the hands, wrists, and knees are leading to swelling, pain, and, over time, irreversible joint damage [18]. Multiple studies have indicated that following a vegan diet may be linked to a reduced risk of developing autoimmune diseases [19]. A 2015 study (n = 50) observed reductions in inflammatory scores in overweight or obese, otherwise healthy, participants randomized to a 2-month vegan, vegetarian, or pescovegetarian dietary intervention (p < 0.05) compared to those placed on a semi-vegetarian or omnivorous diet. Subjects in all five groups were counseled to choose low-fat foods, but only the vegan participants met the mean percentage energy from fat and saturated fat ($\leq 30\%$ energy from fat and $\leq 7\%$ energy from saturated fat) recommendations [20]. It is well-established that in autoimmune conditions, polyphenols possess strong antioxidant properties that help counteract the damaging effects of reactive species produced by an overactive immune response. Polyphenols play a significant antioxidant role in autoimmune disorders, helping to reduce the damaging effects of reactive species produced by an overactive immune system. Moreover, these polyphenolic compounds (resveratrol (RSV), epigallocatechin (EGCG), capsaicin and curcumin) serve as biologically active agents with notable immunomodulatory effects [22].

Multiple Sclerosis

Multiple sclerosis is a long-term autoimmune condition that causes chronic inflammation in the central nervous system. Its exact cause remains uncertain, likely due to the complex interplay of various contributing factors. While nutrition is thought to play a role in the development of MS,

current evidence has not clearly linked any specific dietary pattern to changes in inflammation or overall health outcomes in individuals with the disease [23].

A recent study suggested that dietary choices can influence the levels of neurotransmitter precursors we consume, potentially affecting behavior. For instance, participants who ate a breakfast with a high carbohydrate-to-protein ratio demonstrated less fairness in a money distribution exercise known as the ultimatum game, compared to those who consumed a lower-ratio meal. Strang et al. observed that blood levels of serotonin and dopamine precursors were predictive of participants' behavior in the task, and these levels were directly influenced by the nutritional composition of the meal consumed beforehand [25]. 144 multiple sclerosis patients took a low-fat diet for 34 years. For each of three categories of neurological disability (minimum, moderate, severe) patients who adhered to the prescribed diet (≤ 20 g fat/day) showed significantly less deterioration and much lower death rates than did those who consumed more fat than prescribed (> 20 g fat/day). The greatest benefit was seen in those with minimum disability at the start of the trial; in this group, when those who died from non-MS diseases were excluded from the analysis, 95% survived and remained physically active [26].

Type 1 Diabetes (T1D)

Diabetes mellitus is a systemic metabolic disorder characterized by persistent high blood glucose levels, resulting from impaired insulin secretion, reduced insulin effectiveness, or a combination of both. It affects the metabolism of carbohydrates, fats, and proteins [27]. Type 1 diabetes results from the immune system attacking the insulin-producing cells of the pancreas, ultimately leading to a significant reduction in insulin production. This condition typically develops in younger individuals and requires lifelong reliance on insulin therapy for blood sugar regulation [28].

Research from China has shown that consuming high glycemic index and glycemic load foods especially rice, may elevate the risk of developing diabetes. In contrast, studies in the United States found that replacing white rice with brown rice was linked to a reduced risk in both men and women. Additionally, the intake of trans fats, as well as both vegetable and animal ghee, has been associated with an increased diabetes risk. Follow-up research also revealed that

diets high in saturated and total fats are correlated with a greater likelihood of developing the condition [29]. There is no evidence that people with type 1 diabetes generally estimate their meals quantitatively for energy, fat and protein content in order to derive an additional insulin bolus [30].

A large number of studies have now been published investigating the effects of low GI diets in the

management. A previous meta-analysis of 14 studies, encompassing 356 individuals with type 1 and type 2 diabetes, concluded that low-glycemic index (GI) diets can enhance blood sugar regulation comparably to medications designed to manage postprandial glucose spikes [31].

Table 1 Substituting high GI foods for low GI alternatives [32].

High GI food	Lower GI alternative
Bread (white or whole meal)	Dense, whole-grain breads
Puffed and flaked breakfast cereals	Unrefined cereals (e.g., rolled oats or natural muesli)
Plain biscuits or crackers	Biscuits made with dried fruit, oats, and whole grains
Potato	Baby new potatoes, sweet potatoes, and corn
Most types of rice	Basmati rice, pearled barley, quinoa, cracked wheat, pasta, noodles

A Cochrane systematic review, which analyzed data from 11 randomized controlled trials lasting at least four weeks, found that low-glycemic index diets not only enhance glycemic control in individuals with diabetes but also lower the likelihood of hypoglycemic episodes. This outcome is especially important, as better blood glucose regulation is often linked to a heightened risk of hypoglycemia which is a major obstacle to reaching optimal glycemic targets, particularly for those living with type 1 diabetes [33].

Inflammatory Bowel Disease (IBD: Crohn’s and Ulcerative Colitis)

Inflammatory bowel disease, which includes Crohn’s disease and ulcerative colitis, has been on the rise globally, with growing incidence rates and broader geographic spread is highlighting its emergence as a

worldwide health concern. IBD is a genetically influenced condition believed to be initiated by various environmental triggers [34]. Epidemiological research suggests that dietary patterns rich in animal fats and poor in fruits and vegetables are most frequently linked to a heightened risk of developing IBD [35]. In March 2021, a 35-year-old non-smoking woman sought dietary consultation following the birth of her second child. She had been diagnosed with ulcerative colitis, exhibiting symptoms such as the presence of blood and mucus in her stool, pronounced flatulence, and significant constipation. A colonoscopy, along with biopsy samples, confirmed a moderately active form of UC affecting a 30 cm segment from the anal verge [36]. The dietary recommendations were based on a WFPBD.

Table 2: Dietary Pattern Before and After the WFPB Intervention [37]

Case 1	Usual Diet Before Intervention	Whole Food Plant-Based Diet
Grains	White pasta (twice a week) white rice (twice a week), white bread, white crackers (daily)	Buckwheat, millet, quinoa (daily), rice (once per week), wholemeal pasta and wholemeal bread (twice per week)
Beans, pulses	A variety (lentils, giant beans, black eyed peas, mung beans) once or twice per week	Red lentils, brown lentils, chickpeas, giant beans, mung beans (small portions e.g. 3 tablespoons daily), tofu twice per week
Vegetables	Green leafy vegetables (daily), okra, green beans, aubergines, peas once or	Broccoli, cauliflower carrots, sweet potato, potato, aubergine, tomato, mushrooms, peas, red bell

	twice per week	peppers, green leafy veggies (a variety of 3 chosen vegetables daily)
Fruit	Banana every other day - rarely other fruits (every 3 weeks)	Banana (daily) strawberries (every other day), blueberries (daily), pineapple (daily), avocado (every other day), green and red apple (daily)
Nuts and seeds	None	Peanut butter, pumpkin seeds, linseeds or sunflower seeds (4-5 times per week)
Meat	Chicken, 3 times per week, red meat, twice per week, fish every other week	None
Dairy	Yoghurt and milk rarely (once every month)	None
Processed foods	Refined oil, sugar, butter, chocolate, sweets made with eggs and butter, fried foods, meat-based take-aways 3- 4 times per week	Vegan cheese (twice per week), plant-based milk (daily)

Following a Whole-Food, Plant-Based Diet, the patient experienced gradual symptom relief, with complete resolution over a few months. A follow-up colonoscopy showed no inflammation in the sigmoid colon and significant healing in the rectum [38]. Lupus (SLE) is an autoimmune disease where the immune system attacks healthy tissue, potentially

damaging multiple organs simultaneously. Psoriatic arthritis is a chronic autoimmune disease that causes inflammation in both the skin and joints. Commonly associated with psoriasis, it can affect individuals of any gender, with most diagnoses occurring between the ages of 40 and 50 [40].

Table 2 Dietary Pattern Before Adopting Whole Food Plant-Based Diet (WFPBD) [42].

Usual diet before WFPD	
Grains	Pasta, white flour, wholemeal flour, white rice
Pulses	Red lentils
Vegetables	2 portions daily; potatoes, carrots, peas, sweetcorn, tomatoes, cucumbers
Fruit	2 portions daily; apples, bananas, oranges
Nuts and seeds	None
Processed foods	Oil, textured vegetable protein, vegan cheese, vegan sausages, soya cream, vegan mayonnaise, soya,margarine, pastries, cakes, biscuits, ice cream, hummus, sugar

Case Study

A 40-year-old female teacher with PsA, diagnosed in 2003 and managed with methotrexate for 15 years. In

late 2017, she adopted a whole-food, plant-based diet, excluding processed foods, added sugars, salt, and oils. Within six months, she tapered off methotrexate and remained symptom-free by early 2018 [41].

Table 4 Dietary Pattern After Adopting Whole Food Plant-Based Diet (WFPBD) [43].

WFPBD adopted by the patient	
Grains	Wholemeal bread, wholemeal pasta, amaranth, millet, oat groats, wholegrain rice, barley, rye, buckwheat
Pulses	2+ servings daily; chickpeas, black beans, kidney beans, peas; occasionally, tofu and tempeh
Vegetables	5+ portions daily; mushrooms, onions, garlic, tomatoes, chives, potatoes, sweet potatoes, carrots,parsnips, artichokes, yakon, radish, pumpkin,

Fruit	cauliflower, broccoli, green leafy vegetables, seaweed 5+ portions daily; berries, apples, pears, peaches, bananas, oranges, grapes, mango
Nuts and seeds	1+ portion daily; flaxseed, walnuts, almonds, cashews, peanuts, chia seeds, pumpkin seeds, sesame seeds, sunflower seeds
Processed foods	1 portion daily of soya milk; sauerkraut; occasionally soya sauce, miso

This is rare, as less than 2% of PsA patients achieve remission without medication. The diet led to normalized inflammatory markers and no further symptoms, though occasional diet deviations caused brief stiffness and joint locking [45].

Comparing WFPBD with Other Diets in Autoimmune Disease Management

Diets	Pros	Cons
WFPD	Reduced inflammation in Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA) and improved inflammatory markers WFPBD associated with better glycemic control and lower hypoglycemia risk through low-GI food choices Patient cases demonstrate remission without medication when WFPBD is strictly followed	Long-term nutritional adequacy (e.g., B12, omega-3) needs monitoring Requires strict dietary compliance deviation may trigger symptom relapse May not work universally individual variability in gut response and immune modulation [46]
Mediterranean Diet	Rich in antioxidants, polyphenols, monounsaturated fats (olive oil) Anti-inflammatory & immunomodulatory effects	May be hard to replicate outside Mediterranean regions Some foods (like red wine or seafood) may not be suitable for all Effects come from whole-diet synergy, not single foods [47]
Paleo Diet Effects	↓ TSH, Tg Ab, TPO Ab in majority of cases ↑ T3 & T4 hormone levels Resolution of HT and GD in some cases	Highly restrictive (e.g., no gluten/grains) Possible nutrient deficiencies [48]
Ketogenic Diet	Improved cognitive and motor functions in experimental autoimmune models (EAE, CPZ) Reduced pro-inflammatory cytokines, microglial and astrocyte activation	One study found no significant effect on EDSS, QoL, or fatigue after 12 weeks More large-scale trials are needed (e.g., 111 participants for 80% power) [49]

Challenges & Limitations of WFPBD for Autoimmune Patients

A Whole Food Plant-Based Diet holds therapeutic promise for managing autoimmune conditions, yet its implementation is accompanied by multifaceted challenges. Nutrient deficiencies, especially in vitamin B12, iron, and long-chain omega-3 fatty acids (EPA/DHA) are among the most prominent concerns, as plant-exclusive diets lack these in bioavailable forms. Deficiency in B12 can impair nerve function and

exacerbate fatigue, while iron and omega-3 insufficiencies may affect immune modulation and cognitive clarity. Adherence to WFPBD can be hindered by cultural preferences, social events, financial cost, and lack of access to fresh produce. This often limits long-term feasibility, especially in diverse populations or those unfamiliar with plant-centric culinary practices [50].

Future Research Directions

In future research, there is a growing need for large-scale, long-term randomized controlled trials to better understand the impacts of whole food plant-based diets on human health. These trials would help to establish causality and provide more robust evidence of their effectiveness across diverse populations and health conditions. Additionally, the integration of precision nutrition, which tailors dietary recommendations to individual genetic, microbiome, and lifestyle factors, holds promising potential for optimizing the benefits of WFPBDs [51].

Furthermore, exploring the potential synergies between WFPBDs and emerging medical therapies, such as pharmacogenomics or gene editing, could enhance therapeutic outcomes and open new avenues for personalized healthcare interventions [52].

Conclusion

This review has highlighted the growing body of evidence supporting the therapeutic value of Whole-Food, Plant-Based Diets in the context of autoimmune diseases. Numerous clinical studies and case reports illustrate significant reductions in symptom severity across a range of autoimmune conditions, including rheumatoid arthritis, inflammatory bowel disease, type 1 diabetes, lupus, and psoriatic arthritis. These improvements are often linked to reductions in systemic inflammation, favorable shifts in gut microbiota composition, and the intake of nutrient-dense, anti-inflammatory foods.

While the prospect of disease modification is promising, claims of complete disease reversal should be approached with caution. Although exceptional cases have demonstrated drug-free remission, especially when dietary adherence is strict, these outcomes are not yet generalizable. The current evidence does not suffice to position WFPBDs as a standalone cure but rather as a complementary approach that may support conventional treatment strategies and improve quality of life.

In conclusion, a WFPBD represents a sustainable and potentially impactful lifestyle intervention in the management of autoimmune diseases. However, its full therapeutic scope remains to be defined. Large-scale, long-term randomized controlled trials are urgently needed to establish causality, refine patient-specific recommendations, and evaluate the

integration of WFPBDs into standard autoimmune care protocols.

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